

MAIN REQUIREMENTS FOR DIGITAL BANK: INVESTOR PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: This article gives you a brief overview on digital banking. The advantages of digital banks over traditional banks are explained in terms of divisions. There is also information on the income of the largest banks in the world in the field of digital banking. There is also detailed information about the current capabilities of digital banking.

Keywords: Digital banking, IT systems, Digital payments, Fintech, P2P.

Digital banking is an exciting investment opportunity and an inevitable business step, as older banks can no longer adequately serve the needs of their customers in the digital age. Traditional banks that cannot achieve the digital revolution cannot meet customer demand.

With neither additional costs for real estate nor large costs for repairing outdated IT systems, digital banks are more likely to be part-time employees over a number of years of operation compared to traditional banks. Expects to grow billions of dollars in balances. For example, Atom Bank in the UK plans to turn into a £ 5bn balance business with only 340 full-time employees in five years, while the old bank Metro has a balance sheet of 2,200.

However, it is clear that the majority of digital banking employees will be engineers and data scientists, although, as always, the role of sales and marketing should not be overlooked.

Monetization and value acquisition are of great importance to investors. Compared to older banks, digital banks can create value in many ways:

Digital payments. Digital payments form the basis of monetization. These include local and foreign mobile and online payments, as well as mobile P2P connections. Digital payments allow banks to increase payment and interest income and cover a wide range of customers with a variety of services; Digital banks can process digital payments more efficiently than existing banks, allowing them to increase market share at competitive prices and access 2.5 billion unpaid and unpaid banks.

Digital wallet. A digital wallet is a must for ecosystems based on digital commerce and value-added services. In addition, it optimizes transaction costs and banking financing costs for customers.

Digital trade and banking products. The sale of banking products using artificial intelligence, such as deposits, loans and mortgages, is carried out directly through channels, including social networks. This is largely in line with changes in consumer preferences and behavioral trends in e-commerce aimed at customers who are well-versed in Generation Y and technology.

Multi-channel. An integrated and continuous multi-channel approach to sales increases the bank's share of customer wallets and increases customer loyalty, thereby significantly varying customer acceptance rates.

Digital financial planner and robot consulting. An artificial intelligence-based digital financial planner manages monthly revenue, repeat payments, savings and investments, and enhances the interaction between digital banking and customers. The bank plays the role of a reliable shepherd and determines the financial needs of the client's life cycle. This represents a logical continuation of the scope of trust between digital banking and customers. In this model, clients rely on robotic

consulting services to optimize investment portfolios based on personal goals and preferences, adjust them on a regular basis and record additional results, and allocate resources correctly for each stage of the client's journey to all digital objects.

Smart big data. Sophisticated analytics allow digital banking to turn their data into a more personalized customer service focused on data monetization.

Emphasis on SME. AI and big data-based credit models allow small and medium-sized enterprises that do not have 45 million banks globally to manage risk for small and medium-sized enterprises. As of 2018, banks in Scandinavia, the UK and Western Europe accounted for half or more of the new revenue from digital communication-related activities in most products, such as deposits and time deposits, banking services for small and medium businesses. predicted to have a program.

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